

Redefine value and encourages economists to rethink traditional approaches

Shed

September 24, 2024

[BOOK REVIEW]

Top reviews from the United States

 Shed

★★★★★ Verified Purchase

A New Perspective on Economics

Reviewed in the United States on September 24, 2024

This book offers a fresh take on how economics can evolve to better address modern challenges like environmental crises and AI.

It draws on ideas from physics and quantum theory to redefine value and encourages economists to rethink traditional approaches.

Screenshot. A Review of “[Better Economics for the Earth](#)”. Reviewed in the United States on September 24, 2024 [1]

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It draws on ideas from physics and quantum theory to redefine value and encourages economists to rethink traditional approaches.

I really liked some of the figures and illustrations used to explain complex concepts—they really helped clarify the ideas presented.

It's a thoughtful read for those interested in the intersection of science and economics.

(*) Note: This column reprints Shed's review appearing on the Amazon page of the title: <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/RK6Y6IAS1O3BP/>, with some light edits for clarity and fitting our house style.

References

[1] Shed. (2024). A New Perspective on Economics. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/RK6Y6IAS1O3BP/>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOD98L5K44>

